

Is world trade slowing down? New evidence on trade-income elasticity

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Abstract

This paper completes and updates the research on the nature of the so-called global trade slowdown. Not only do we explain and discuss the determinants of this phenomenon, but we also offer an empirical description of the recent evolution of trade and trade elasticity. With the purpose of testing whether this is a structural phenomenon or not, we build an Error Correction Model for both world and regional data on trade and income using data from the World Bank for the period 1970-2017. World, OECD and Asian countries trade elasticity figures show a remarkable reduction after the hyperglobalization period (1986-2001), opposed to Latin American ones whose trade volume has not stagnated so much. This slowdown might have major consequences for any country, but especially for those having relied more intensively on trade as an engine for growth.

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I.- INTRODUCTION

Global trade of goods and services had shown a relevant increase during the approximately three decades prior to the global financial crisis in 2008, having outperformed growth in global output over the years. However, recent years have witnessed a deceleration in real growth of global trade, in particular since its recovery after the Global Trade Collapse (GTC) of 2009. More concretely, from 1980 to 2007, global trade real growth (6.1%) almost doubled real GDP growth (3.5%); in contrast, from 2012 to 2015, figures on trade growth were much lower (2.9%), showing an expansion even lower than the one registered in total output (3.4%).¹

This stagnation in world trade has been called the “global trade slowdown”. One important question is whether this is mostly a cyclical downturn, reflecting slow growth in GDP, or whether it is fundamentally reflecting a permanent change towards lower increases in world trade flows (in comparison with GDP).² In the latter case, this would imply that the “hyperglobalization” period (Rodrik, 2011) has come to an end and world trade will converge towards a “new normal”, which would resemble the period before the mid-1980s³.

The aim of this paper is not to assess whether the pre-crisis level of international trade was excessive, and in fact there are opposing views regarding this debate; in any case this slowdown will signify a new paradigm. Mainstream literature has insisted on the benefits of international trade through innovation and productivity spillovers as an engine of growth and not only for developing countries (Melitz and Ottaviano, 2008; Taglioni, 2016), whereas other authors have pointed out the negative side-effects of hyperglobalization, (Rodrik, 2011; Stiglitz 2017). If the slowdown in global trade becomes a long-run phenomenon because it is basically of a structural nature, it would mean a new regime for the global economy, affecting almost every country in

¹ A note of caution must be made regarding trade data; the exact figures depend on whether they are calculated in PPP or in dollars (Ollivaud and Schwellnuss, 2015).

² In the literature, the concrete distinction of this phenomenon as being explained mainly by structural factors is not quite clear, but apparently there is a commonly shared view about the prolonged reduction in trade’s rate of growth; but at the same time it is not clear whether the factors of the trade slowdown are structural or not.

³ Foreign direct investment flows (FDI) constitute another very relevant aspect of the globalization process, and are closely linked to trade flows. In fact, based on UNCTAD estimates, one third of international trade is intra-firm trade. FDI flows have also diminished considerably in recent years and as we discuss in the next section the fall in FDI by multinational enterprises (especially those developing a vertical strategy) is a possible explanation for world trade stagnation, but in this paper we solely discuss trade flows.

the world. This preoccupation for pro-trade analysts is evident, for instance by Haugh et al. (2016), when stating that the favourable structural factors existing during the booming trade years are unlikely to keep on sustaining that dynamism in trade unless substantial policy actions are taken. This brief overview of the debate reveals why analyzing the factors behind the trade slowdown is a relevant issue not only for academics, but also in the first place for institutions (Borin et al., 2016) and policymakers in general.

The objective of this article is to test whether the global trade slowdown is essentially a structural phenomenon or not. Following the most frequently used procedure to do so, we compute an Error Correction Model (ECM) aimed at explaining the evolution of the relationship between trade and income throughout the time.

This paper contributes to the empirical literature on the explanation of the global trade slowdown phenomenon, particularly updating the works of Constantinescu et al. (2016, 2018) or Ollivaud and Schwellnus (2015). Not only do we utilize a more comprehensive time span but also obtain trade-income elasticity estimations for different geographical areas, with the purpose of testing whether trade slowdown affects differently the following regions: World, OECD, Asia, and Latin American countries.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the factors explaining trade slowdown and the empirical literature review, section III presents the stylized facts about this phenomenon, section IV is about the econometric strategy and results, and finally, section V concludes.

II.- FACTORS EXPLAINING THE GLOBAL TRADE SLOWDOWN: THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Before turning to the causes of the global trade slowdown, it is important to mention that the dating of this phenomenon should be taken with some flexibility. However, there is an apparent consensus (Constantinescu et al., 2018) that trade growth accelerated—in comparison to the 70s—from the mid-1980s to the beginning of the 2000s, reaching a trade elasticity of around 2, and slowing down afterwards especially from 2008, (trade elasticity fell to approx. 1). Anyway, regarding its causes, the global slowdown is a complex phenomenon, as shown by the long list of determinants put forward by the literature. Moreover, whether they are of a cyclical or structural (long-term) nature is not neatly defined, so we will try to do our best to mention the

most cited studies and classify them as clearly as possible, admitting that they are neither contradictory nor exhaustive.

One of the main structural factors to be cited is evidently the recent trade liberalization halt. The progressive opening of trade, as witnessed especially in the 1990s,⁴ has come apparently to an end.⁵ In consequence, the trade-creation effect put forward by Viner (1950) is no longer promoting commerce flows. Going even further, we can talk about some signs of protectionist trade policy. Although there has not been a strong increase in tariffs, non-tariff barriers (such as rules of origin or sanitary and phytosanitary SPS measures) are increasingly being employed (Wozniak and Galar, 2018), and recent trade policy developments, such as the USA–China trade tension, suggest the possibility of an incoming trade war. However, import trade restrictions are only showing a slight rise, as revealed by the WTO trade restrictiveness indicators (WTO, 2018).

Another structural factor of major importance is the attenuation of commerce cost reduction. The previous spread of the utilization of ICT in transport and logistics, as well as containerization, which started in the 1960s, are almost already exhausted as crucial trade increase factors, at least since the 2000s (Hummels, 2007).

Other long-term determinants which are derived as predictions from the trade gravity model (Anderson, 2011)⁶ are that the smaller and the higher number of countries there are, the higher the international trade will be. In the 1990s there was an increase in their number and a reduction of their average dimension, mainly due to the split of USSR and Yugoslavia (Escaith and Miroudot 2015). Those historical events will neither occur again nor provoke a new trade increase.⁷ Another prediction arising from the same model is that trade is maximized when countries are of similar size; in this regard, income convergence of large developing countries and the slower growth amongst mature industrialized ones have been a relevant engine of trade

⁴ The exceptionally high trade growth from 1986 to 2000 was favoured by the creation of NAFTA, WTO, and the European Single Market together with the accession of transition economies to the world market.

⁵ Clear examples to mention are the impossibility of signing the WTO Doha Round or the failure of new commercial integration schemes such as the TTIP or the TAIP.

⁶ The gravity model is an empirical workhorse model for explaining bilateral trade flows, which serves to make predictions regarding structural factors affecting trade.

⁷ Although there are some nationalist tensions, for instance in Europe (Scotland, Catalonia, Basque Country), nowadays there is a low likelihood for there to be a relevant increase of countries.

expansion in the past decades. As Escaith and Miroudot (2015) state, income convergence has slowed down since the 2000s.

Now, arising from the classical Ricardian theory, a higher degree of product specialization amongst countries boosts trade flows. In this regard, a rise in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDP pc) provokes an expansion in product specialization, but only up to a certain GDP pc threshold level (\$25,000 Purchasing Power Parity PPP, Cadot et al., 2011); had this threshold level been reached since the 2000s amongst some large emerging countries (BRICs), this could also have had a negative impact on trade.

Additionally, especially among emerging countries, structural change provoked by progressive economic development has caused an increase in services' contribution to GDP and demand. In consequence, the global slowdown could be partially explained by the structural shift towards services since services are less tradable than goods; on the one hand, some services are not tradable at all (consumption and "production" should take place in the same location, e. g. education, health, public services...), and on the other because services are usually subject to more trade frictions than goods. Therefore, we can talk about a compositional effect: when demand switches towards services, following Engel's law, countries trade relatively less, explaining the global slowdown as a consequence. This is coherent with Irwin (2002), who states that the increase in trade-income elasticity for the long period 1950-2000 is due to the higher share of manufacturing goods over GDP.

The increase of China's share of total world manufacturing exports during the last decades (from 3% in 1990 up to 25% in 2016) suggests that any structural change in the Chinese economy may affect world trade in the long run. In this sense, the apparent shift from an export-driven trade growth model to another one based on internal demand is a structural factor, which could explain the global trade slowdown in the long run (Hong et al., 2017). China's trade growth before the crisis reached annually 20% (from 2002 to 2007), but recent data show a clear stagnation in trade growth: only 1.5% in 2015.

Finally, a frequently mentioned suspect is the evolving nature of production within global value chains during the last 30 years. Some innovations in the production process such as the international fragmentation of production have permitted delocalizing different stages of the

value chain to less costly locations. This pattern of trade contrasts with the conventional (Heckscher-Ohlin) comparative advantage trade model used for final goods.⁸

These global value chains are mostly driven and managed by multinational enterprises using vertical foreign direct investment strategies to reduce mainly labour costs (Baldwin, 2011). This phenomenon has predominantly involved developing and emerging countries,⁹ especially China, and in consequence it has provoked a “genuine” trade-creation effect (Escaith et al., 2010), due to the expansion of intermediate trade in inputs.

In addition to this trade-creation effect of GVCs, there is also a purely accounting side effect that inflates trade values mostly in the countries the most involved in that trade, including many small industrialized countries. According to UNCTAD (2017) estimates, trade in intermediate inputs accounts for approximately 45% of total trade in goods and services.

However, there are signs of some recent reshoring strategies by firms, as a reaction to a seemingly overshooting of the international fragmentation of production. Timmer et al. (2016), by developing a global import intensity measure for production, estimate that international fragmentation has stalled since 2010.¹⁰ Apparently, the highly complex fragmentation of some firms has not brought the expected benefits, so reshoring has been revealed as an alternative. The literature (Crozet et al., 2015; ECB, 2016) has mentioned some general underlying drivers for this reshoring: firstly, the increasing capabilities of developing countries to produce at home upstream products for domestic demand, as happened in China. Secondly, the increased automation of industrial processes is already causing a certain degree of reshoring.¹¹ Other drivers might be the changes in relative labour costs, or policy measures such as protectionist

⁸ Baldwin (2011) goes even further, pointing out that there is an international specialization in “tasks” and not products.

⁹ The share of foreign value added in total exports reaches 30% in East and South East Asian countries (UNCTAD, 2013).

¹⁰ In the EU, between 2011 and 2013, the intermediate-to-final goods ratio decreases from 1.93% to 1.85% (ILO, 2015). In the USA during 2013, it was estimated that between 30,000 and 40,000 new manufacturing jobs were created in America due to reshoring (Vanchan et al., 2018).

¹¹ Other managerial drivers, such as changes in the business context (Martínez-Mora and Merino, 2014), managerial errors (Kinkel and Maloca, 2009), and the deep interconnections inside the value chain (Steinle and Schiele, 2008) are also often mentioned in management literature.

pressures.¹² However, a word of caution is needed, since empirical evidence of reshoring is still scarce and far from being conclusive. In fact, Baldwin (2016) states that it is unclear whether international fragmentation will restart again, especially in the case of services.

Turning lastly to cyclical factors related to the exacerbated effect of the business cycle on trade, recent studies have put emphasis on two channels through which trade slowdown can be interpreted: firstly, the so-called GVC composition effect, which states that as long as durable goods' sectors are more vertically integrated within GVCs, together with the fact that this type of goods show a higher income elasticity, when there is an income shock, it causes a higher impact on trade, thereby increasing trade-income elasticity (Bems et al., 2010; Ceglowski, 2014). The second channel is called the supply chain effect or Bullwhip effect. This states that firms involved in offshoring strategies tend to accumulate more buffer stocks of inventories to prevent from mistakes in sales forecasts. In consequence, when there is a downturn in sales, firms employ inventories, and disproportionately suspend new purchases of inputs. This strong fall in inputs' purchases can exacerbate the sensibility of trade to external income shocks in comparison with regular trade (Alessandria et al., 2011; Altomonte et al., 2012).

Another cyclical composition effect is the higher import propensity of investment in comparison with other components of aggregate demand, such as public spending or even consumption. Investment's relative stagnation with respect to public spending, due to its higher procyclicality, might explain the fall in total trade-income elasticity during the recent financial crisis (Bussière et al., 2013). Public expenditure acquires more non-tradable goods and services and additionally has a higher home bias, which explains its lower import intensity (ECB, 2016).

From the supply side, the literature has highlighted the relatively sluggish GDP growth amongst some relevant import-intensive countries (especially Eurozone ones), which has also reduced trade volumes (Francis and Morel, 2015; Slopek, 2015). The current contribution of intra-European trade to world trade expansion is about half of the amount it represented in the 1990s.

Financial constraints have also logically played a role during the global trade collapse because most international trade transactions require the incurring of costs, such as finding export opportunities or creating foreign distribution networks. Moreover, exporters rely heavily on financial advances because production costs are borne long before revenues are obtained, and

¹² For instance, the "America First" Initiative or "China 2025".

additionally, to hedge for financial risks associated with export operations (European Central Bank , 2016).

Lastly, as mentioned by International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2016) and Wozniak and Galar (2018), the commodity prices cycle may also have caused a reduction in trade in 2014 and 2015. Commodity prices sank during those years, and the reduction in export revenue amongst commodity exporters provoked an increase in capital outflows, currency depreciations, fiscal problems, as well as political unrest. These factors favoured a reduction in investment goods' imports, thus pushing down imports even further.

Once having listed all these drivers affecting trade, we can arrive at the following consideration: structural factors are causing a permanent reduction in trade elasticity, whereas cyclical factors, per se will depend on the global business cycle. Therefore, in section 4 we want to test whether there has been a reduction in long-run elasticity and whether there is a higher pro-cyclicality of trade flows.

However, before moving to the econometric model and the results, a brief review of the empirical literature should be carried out. This paper follows two strands of the empirical literature about trade slowdown. The first has to do with the large amount of research done about the specific causes that provoked the sudden and severe global trade collapse of 2008-2009 following the financial crisis. Although there are some discrepancies about the relative importance of each one, the bulk of the empirical research reveals that the main determinants were the big fall of aggregate demand (especially of its most trade intensive components) and also the credit crunch affecting trade financing (Bems et al., 2010; Bussière et al., 2013). However, our work is linked more closely to the papers concentrating their focus on the changes in the long-run elasticity between trade and income. The most recent papers include the GTC years too, and therefore, their main interest, as in our case, is to analyse whether the GTS is connected to changes in the long-run trade elasticity. Most of these studies use ECM techniques in order to detect the short- and long-run elasticity over different time periods.¹³

In this sense, Irwin (2002) analyzes very long-run trends between world trade and income. The results he obtains show that from 1950 to 2000, trade grew slightly more rapidly than income (with a trade elasticity of 1.7) and that apparently there was a structural break between the mid-1980s and 2000 due principally to a new, much more liberal, regime for trade under the auspices

¹³ Only the paper of Freund (2009) does it for several areas but she uses an OLS technique.

of GATT and World Trade Organization (WTO). During this last period, trade became extremely responsive to changes in income, reaching an elasticity of 3.4. Freund (2009) examines the impact of past global downturns on trade flows and finds that by employing an OLS technique from 1960 to 2007, the elasticity of global trade volumes to world GDP has increased gradually from approx. 2.0 in the 60s to 3.7 in the 2000s (2000-2007). Another result is that during severe downturns, trade tends to be more responsive than during more tranquil times. Finally, the largest elasticity is for East Asian countries, for which the figure is approx. 4.5 from 1995 to 2007.

Escaith et al. (2010) also find an increase of long-run elasticity during the 1980s and 1990s before noting its fall in the 2000s. However, their figures are considerably lower (probably because they restricted the sample to 24 OECD countries). More importantly, for their last period (2000-2009), the elasticity falls from 2.8 in the 1990s to 1.9. Another study (Martinez-Martin, 2016) using an ECM panel technique finds, like the one of Irwin (2002), that trade response to income change in the long run for the period of 1960 to 2000 is approx. 1.4, which later increased slightly from 2001 to 2009 and fell to 1.2 from 2010 to 2015. For him, the apparent main cause of this small slowdown is a levelling off of the GVC.

Constantinescu et al. (2016), obtain a decreasing long-run elasticity from 2.2 (1986-2000) to 1.3 (2001-2013), quite similar to that found by Ollivaud and Schwellnus (2015), but a little lower than that for Escaith et al. (2010) who calculated it at 1.9. Nakajima et al. (2016), using quarterly data, obtain a long-run estimation of this parameter of 1.0 for the period 2009-2015 that is slightly lower than for the previous period (1995-2008: 1.5). Their results are very proximate to those of Martinez-Martin (2016, 1.2): they attributed this lower elasticity to the expansion of in-house production in China and the already-mentioned deceleration of GVC expansion. Finally, the recent paper of Constantinescu et al. (2018), also using annual and quarterly data, shows that the elasticity in the long run has declined from 2.5 (2001-2007) to 1.0 (2008-2015) due mainly to a slowing pace of international vertical specialization.

III.- STYLIZED FACTS

In order to make a preliminary assessment of the relative relevance of structural and cyclical components on trade elasticity at the world level and the other regions analyzed, we have applied the Hodrick-Prescott filter for the annual data of imports (goods and services) and of trade-income elasticity. Trade-income elasticity has been calculated in the usual way as the

ratio between the annual change in imports of goods and services and the change in GDP, both of them measured in constant 2010 US dollars.

The data used in this study are annual observations of GDP and imports of goods and services and the analyzed period is 1970-2017.¹⁴ The data have been sourced from the World Development Indicators of the World Bank. The units of the data are in constant 2010 US dollars. Logarithmic transformations have been used for all the variables.

We perform our analysis using time series data for four geographical world regions separately: (i) the world as a whole, (ii) OECD countries, (iii) Asian countries, and (iv) Latin America (see Annex 1 for concrete countries in each group).

In Figure 1 it can be seen that after the overshooting of 2010 after the GTC, imports trade growth declines considerably until 2017. The average growth for this period (2011-2017) is 3.6% below the previous average for between 1985 and 2007 (6.1%) and more in line with the 1971-1984 period (4.39%).¹⁵ It can be also deduced that the cyclical component of world imports is negative during those years in which world GDP growth is below trend, something that will be discussed in more detail below in Figure 3.

¹⁴ Quarterly data are not available for the long period we analysed, but testing the long-run relationships with annual data is not conceptually different from using quarterly data (Hakkio and Rush, 1991)

¹⁵ Using data from the WTO for merchandise exports yields a similar evolution for the periods commented on in the main text, although figures are slightly higher since the WTO source only makes reference to merchandise.

Figure 1.

Decomposition of trend and cycle of global imports of goods and services

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

Additionally, it is worth mentioning that during all of this period of more than 30 years, there have been only three years with a negative growth rate coinciding with global downturns: namely 1975, 1982, and the much deeper GTC of 2009, the only year with a negative world GDP growth. In fact, the section capturing the cyclical effects is larger during periods of crises, such as the three we mentioned. Additionally, this cyclical part also seems to be larger when the global economy rebounds, as for example in 1976 and more clearly in 2010. Another characteristic is that the trend (structural) component of global trade increased from the period of the mid-1980s until the GTC, which is quite a bit larger than the cyclical component, thereby explaining the bulk of trade increase.¹⁶

¹⁶ The graph shows also the decomposition of trade growth between the trend and the cycle. Coinciding with GDP downturns, the cyclical component (in absolute value) is higher than the structural one in 1975, 1982, 1984, 2009, and 2010.

Figure 2.

Ten-year moving average of imports of goods and services income elasticity

Source: World Bank excluding 2000, 2001, and 2009

Regarding trade-income elasticity evolution, we use a ten-year moving average (Constantinescu et al., 2018) in order to obtain a better and softer picture of its long-run dynamics. In Figure 2, elasticity reaches its trough in the decade of 1974-1983 and a peak in the 10-year window corresponding to 1992-2001; thereafter, there is initially a slight decrease until the window of 2002-2011, from which a stronger downturn is clearly observed until the end of the period in 2017.

Figure 3.

Decomposition of trend and cycle of world imports (goods and services) elasticity

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

In order to gain a more detailed view of the elasticity and its components, Figure 3 shows three important features: first, elasticity increases on average from the beginning of the 1980s until the beginning of the 2000s and thereafter stagnates at a relatively high level. Second, from the early 1980s until the GTC in 2009, the trend component shows a continuous increase and additionally appears to be significantly larger than the cyclical one. Finally, not only elasticity, but also its trend component, slowly decreases from 2010 until 2017.¹⁷ As commented regarding Figure 1, the cyclical component is negative, coinciding with a world GDP growth below its long-term trend.

Moving now to the OECD, Figure 4 shows the evolution of trade elasticity and its components for the same time period.

¹⁷ The elasticity outliers of 1975, 1982, and 2009 are due to the large decrease of imports in those years (in 2009 elasticity is positive since GDP also decreases).

Figure 4.

Decomposition of trend and cycle of OECD imports (goods and services) elasticity

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

Note: 1975 data has been removed because the elasticity figure reaches -20% due to the impact of the oil crisis, making the figure less legible.

Figure 4 shows firstly that the pattern of the elasticity is similar to the world's one, i.e. with an upward tendency from the 1980s to 2000s, a relative stagnation thereafter until the GTC in 2009, and a pronounced decline since 2010.¹⁸ On average, trade elasticity increases from approximately 1% until the mid-80s to 2.4% during the 90s until 2009, but thereafter elasticity has a small fall to 2.1%. Even more pronounced than in world's case, the changes in the structural component explain by far the evolution in trade elasticity, which is especially true after the GTC. Therefore, apparently the slowdown has little to do with the business cycle, but with more structural or fundamental factors. All in all, the case of the OECD countries shows a similar evolution.

¹⁸ GTC in 2009 reveals a low impact on elasticity compared to the World figure, as OECD's imports fall in a similar percentage than in developing and emerging countries, but GDP falls considerably more among OECD countries.

Figure 5.

Decomposition of trend and cycle of Asian imports (goods and services) elasticity

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

Note: 1998 has been removed because the elasticity figure reaches approx. -20% due to the balance of payments crisis of Asian countries, making again the figure less legible.

Regarding Asia, Figure 5 shows that a similar pattern is repeated, although with some peculiarities: elasticity grows on average from the mid-80s to 2001 in comparison to the previous period (1971 to 1984) from 1.5% to 1.8%. This is a small increase in comparison with that occurring in the world or OECD cases, which has to do with the substitution as strong world traders of first Japan by the SE Asian countries and finally by China during these decades; this is why the slowdown in trade could be considered to start earlier (in the mid-90s) than in the other cases commented above. But then again, since 2001 the elasticity drops on average below 1% (0.8%)¹⁹ and in any case, since 2010 the slowdown in trade elasticity is quite clear. Also making a difference with the world and the OECD countries, the largest component of trade elasticity is of a structural nature until the beginning of the 90s, but then the cyclical component and its variations dominate the evolution of trade elasticity; however, and as in the previous cases, since 2010 the drop in trade elasticity appears to be explained principally by structural factors.

¹⁹ In this case, the 2009 GTC has a large and negative effect on elasticity because there is a large drop in imports (11%), but GDP growth remains positive (2%).

Figure 6.

Decomposition of trend and cycle of Latin American imports (goods and services) elasticity

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

This region (Figure 6) shows a quite different evolution. In fact, there are many extreme cases coinciding with repeated critical periods owing to the debt crisis in the beginning of the 80s, the currency crisis in the beginning of the 90s, and the one affecting mostly Argentina in 1999. Apart from GDP volatility, because the region has been hit several times by big crises, trade flows are also quite volatile because of large exchange rate fluctuations. However, the structural component grew until the end of the 90s, but thereafter it diminished quite considerably. Summing up, trade-income elasticity, after its strong growth during the 1990s, seems to have fallen from the beginning of the 2000s. However, the most intense elasticity reduction has taken place after the global trade collapse. This is coincident with the evolution at the world level and for the other regions, except for Latin America. For the world and OECD countries, it is also clear that the trend component has played an important role firstly in the stagnation after 2000 and thereafter in the recent sharp decline of elasticity, revealing somehow the structural nature of the trade slowdown phenomenon. This is not so clear in the case of Asian countries or in Latin America.

IV.- ECONOMETRIC MODELLING AND RESULTS

Our econometric strategy consists of estimating the long-run equilibrium relationship (the trade elasticity, hereafter), the short-run adjustment dynamics between real income (GDP) and trade volumes (proxied by imports of goods and services), and the speed of adjustment to the long-term equilibrium. In order to do so, we follow the literature and use the Error Correction Model (ECM) representation of the first-order autoregressive distributed-lag model (ARDL) of Pesaran and Shin (1999) and Pesaran et al. (2001).

The ARDL bounds test offers several advantages over more traditional cointegration approaches (for instance, Engle and Granger, 1987 and Johansen and Juselius, 1990). The main advantage of the ARDL approach is that it avoids problems of serial correlation and of endogeneity. In addition, this method avoids pretesting of the order of integration, which is associated with other cointegration analyses (Nkoro and Uko, 2016). We only have to ensure that the dependent variable is I(1) and that the regressors are not of an order of integration higher than I(1). This means that one does not have to make the difficult I(0)/I(1) decision (Jordan and Phillips, 2018). Finally, this approach is more efficient and provides better results for small samples (Ghatak and Siddiki, 2001) than other traditional cointegration techniques. We use the ARDL approach to cointegration that, in this study, entails estimating the following ECM:

$$\Delta \ln m_t = \alpha + \beta \Delta \ln y_t + \gamma \ln m_{t-1} + \delta \ln y_{t-1} + e_t \quad (1)$$

Where Δ denotes first differences; m_t is the import of goods and services (constant 2010US\$), and y_t is the real GDP (constant 2010US\$) at time t ; α is a constant and e_t is the error term. The parameter δ portrays long-run effects normalized by γ ($-\delta/\gamma$); the β parameter depicts short-run effects and $(-\gamma)$ is the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium. In the ARDL model, the null hypothesis is stated as $(\delta=0)$. The optimal number of lags of the ECM is chosen using the Akaike Information Criterion. Based on this, we estimate the ARDL (1 1) bound testing approach, which according to the literature is sufficient to ensure a white noise error term (Constantinescu et al., 2018; Irwin, 2002).

Following Pesaran *et al.* (2001), the testing procedure of a long-run relationship between the variables can be based on the *F-test*. The authors derived their asymptotic distributions under the null and proposed critical value bounds, which allows one to accept or reject the null hypothesis that the coefficients on the level variables lagged are jointly equal to zero. If the statistics fall outside of their respective critical upper bound, then we reject the null hypothesis

and we have evidence of a long-run relationship (indicating cointegration). If the statistics are below their respective critical lower bound, then we cannot reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration. Finally, if the statistic falls between the upper and lower critical bounds, then the inference is inconclusive.

As noted, the ARDL model does not need to pre-test the order of integration, but it requires a confirmation for the non-presence of second-order stationarity I(2) in the model. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (1979) and the Phillips-Perron stationarity tests were conducted for all the variables. The results are reported in Table 1. The results show that the real GDP and the volume of imports of goods and services for the different geographical regions are not stationary at the level (with constant term and with trend), but are stationary at the first difference (with constant term and with trend). As a consequence, the ARDL approach can be used to determine the existence of a cointegration relationship between our variables.

Table 1.
Tests for Unit Root. Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillips-Perron Tests

	Level		First Difference	
	Constant	Trend	Constant	Trend
Augmented Dickey Fuller Test (ADF)				
World (m_t)	-.578	-2.173	-5.306***	-5.250***
World (y_t)	-1.170	-4.563**	-5.574***	-5.631***
OECD (m_t)	-.745	-1.733	-5.143***	-5.104***
OECD (y_t)	-2.285	-1.431	-4.616***	-5.310***
Asia (m_t)	-1.064	-1.950	-5.003***	-5.096***
Asia (y_t)	-.362	-2.414	-5.330***	-5.250***
Latin America (m_t)	-.471	-2.261	-4.703***	-4.649***
Latin America (y_t)	-1.808	-3.722	-3.781***	-3.986**
Phillips-Perron Test (z (t)) (PP)				
World (m_t)	-.617	-2.126	-6.487***	-6.428***
World (y_t)	-1.686	-3.618	-5.090***	-5.177***
OECD (m_t)	-.784	-1.685	-6.310***	-6.282***
OECD (y_t)	-3.138**	-1.152	-4.604***	-5.198***
Asia (m_t)	-1.070	-1.753	-5.962***	-6.013***
Asia (y_t)	-.424	-2.176	-5.527***	-5.470***
Latin America (m_t)	-.468	-1.919	-4.919***	-4.857***
Latin America (y_t)	-2.514	-3.406	-4.160***	-4.447***

Note: *, **, *** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively. y_t denotes GDP (constant 2010US\$), m_t imports of goods and services (constant 2010US\$). The lag length based on the Schwarz Information Criterion.

Pesaran et al. (2001) detail different scenarios to carry out the bounds testing approach. In our case, we consider the F statistic of the model with unrestricted intercept and no time. Table 2 shows the values of F-statistics and the critical bounds. The tests lie above the critical upper bound. Therefore, the null hypotheses of no-co integration is rejected implying in all cases the existence of a long run relationship between the variables.

Table 2.
Critical values and bounds test for cointegration. F-statistics

World region	F -statistics	Critical Values at Significant level 0.05	
		I(0)	I(1)
World	5.950*	4.94	5.73
OECD	18.117*	4.94	5.73
Asia	5.740*	4.94	5.73
Latin America	12.010*	4.94	5.73

Note: *indicates that the statistic lies above the upper level of the band. This model is based on the Akaike criterion. F- statistic represent the F-Statistic of the model with unrestricted intercept and no time trend.

After establishing the existence of cointegration in the model, short-run and long-run effects are computed and the results are presented in Tables 3-6 for the four different world regions, respectively. We run our estimations for four periods: the whole period under study (1970-2017) and three sub-periods: 1970-1985, 1986-2000 and 2001-2017. The selection of the sub-periods has been made on the bases of the major waves of globalization.

We also conducted various diagnostic checks to assess the robustness of above estimated results: To test if the residual terms are serially correlated we have use Bresuch-Dodfrey Serial Correlation LM test and the alternative test Durbin-Watson d-statistics. White's test has been used to test homocedasticity.

Table 3.
World

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.115*	-0.17	-.473***	-0.619
Long-run elasticity	1.836***	1.321***	2.155***	1.182*
Short-run elasticity	2.645***	1.835**	2.459***	3.469***
Constant	-3.269***	-2.05	-17.99***	-0.498
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	1.68	2.58	2.48	1.89
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	1.44	5.32	1.68	0.004
Homoscedasticity	7.04	12.5	9.25	13.23
R-squared	0.8219	0.8542	0.5904	0.9538
Observations	47	15	15	17

Note: *, **, *** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively

These results are all in all consistent with the literature we mentioned above. As for where the world is concerned, we detect an increase in the long-run elasticity in the period 1986-2000, compared to the previous one, and a decline thereafter (2001-2017). However, the short-run elasticity exhibits an increase in the 2001-2007 period, suggesting that the global slowdown is not just the result of the financial crisis, but a phenomenon that has more to do with fundamental factors. This also reveals that since 2001, trade flows respond more intensively to the business cycle. A last comment worth mentioning is that our findings reveal on the one hand that the global slowdown started some years before the GTC in 2009 and on the other that the biggest globalizing process has occurred since the mid-1980s. Finally, regarding the diagnosis tests of the models, the Durbin-Watson d-statistic and the Breuch-Godfrey LM test show that there is no serial correlation. The White's test shows that the data is homokedastic because the p-value is not significant.

Table 4.
OECD

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-0.054	-0.431	-0.184	-0.438
Long-run elasticity	2.766***	1.313***	2.727***	2.237***
Short-run elasticity	2.729***	1.627*	2.386***	1.920***
Constant	-3.11***	5.092	-10.272	-17.664*
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	2.35	2.84	2.07	.910
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	1.97	9.92***	.43	7.87***
Homoscedasticity	16.30*	12.02	8.48	12.57
R-squared	0.8683	0.8497	0.8785	0.9103
Observations	47	15	15	17

Note: (1) *,**,*** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively. We have tested that residuals are stationary.

For the OECD countries, Table 2 shows quite similar results as for the whole world. Beyond representing this group of countries, which have the majority share of world trade, elasticity change patterns are slightly smoother: the long-run elasticity does not decrease as much as for the whole world, suggesting that they represent a more cohesive group of countries regarding international production and the corresponding global value chains. Additionally, we would like to highlight that the long-run elasticity for imports amongst OECD countries for the whole period (1970-2017) is somewhat higher than the world one. This means that structural factors, such as the ones promoting an increasingly globalized economy, have had a higher impact on trade growth in OECD countries. The results for the periods 1970-1985 and 2001-2017, however, should be taken with caution since the Durbin-Watson d-statistic and the Breusch-Godfrey LM tests are statistically significant.

Table 5.
Asia

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-0.022	-0.649	-0.263	-.233*
Long-run elasticity	1.088	1.196***	2.154***	.853***
Short-run elasticity	2.653***	-0.347	3.075***	3.777***
Constant	-0.153	-4.96	-9.569	0.611
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	1.98	1.55	1.96	2.62
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	.001	.803	.006	2.563*
Homoscedasticity	9.57	5.10	12.32	9.20
R-squared	0.4168	0.3808	0.8488	0.7816
Observations	47	15	15	17

Note: (1) *,**,*** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively. We have tested that residuals are stationary.

Regarding Asian results, the most remarkable feature is that in the last period (2001-2017), long-run elasticity has fallen more than in the other cases and we guess this is coherent with the idea that reshoring strategies by firms have affected these countries more and that the export-led growth model of China might have started to be replaced by a model that does not depend so much on imported inputs and components. As for the rest of the results, the previous comments apply. The diagnosis tests reveal that there is not serial correlation (in the period 2001-2017 is only statistically significant at the 5% level).

Turning lastly to Latin America, in line with the comments mentioned previously, this is the most divergent area. The lack of significance for the first sub-period (1970-1985) can be attributed to the extended strategies for growth adopted by most of Latin American countries, namely the so-called import substitution policies which decoupled GDP growth from imports. Additionally, during this period, the debt crisis that hit Latin America is also a factor to be considered. In the same vein, as the import substitution growth model was abandoned and the economies opened to world trade and GVCs, elasticity started to reach similar values to the rest of the world. In fact, as can be seen in Table 6, the trade elasticity in the long run even surpassed the world average for the period 1986-2000. Finally, as in the other cases, in the last period, the long-run relationship decreases. The Durbin-Watson d-statistic and the Breuch-Godfrey LM tests are not statistically significant at the level of 5% which means that at that level of significance there is not serial correlation. The White's test shows that the data is homocedastic,

Table 6.
Latin America

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.135***	-0.02	-0.173	-.576***
Long-run elasticity	2.408***	9.764	3.337***	1.823***
Short-run elasticity	3.066***	3.802***	1.917*	1.883***
Constant	-5.852***	-5.245	-12.063	-14.85
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	1.24	2.37	1.28	2.22
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	7.169**	.721	2.960*	3.072*
Homoscedasticity	27.92**	12.74	9.63	12.06
R-squared	0.7007	0.8009	0.4236	0.9407
Observations	47	15	15	17

Note: *, **, *** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively.

We have tested that residuals are stationary.

Finally, we have checked the plots of the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ for each world region and indicate the stability of both long and short run coefficients since the residuals lie within the upper and lower bounds of the critical values. The plots of CUSUM and CUSUMSQ are not reported in this study, but they can be sent by request.

2. Robustness checks

In order to check that our results are robust to the selected breaks years, we have first applied a test for structural breaks. Additionally, we have run the ECM, adding years one by one, and, moreover, we have run the ECM for exports as well in order to check whether there are differences compared to import flows.

The test is conducted with the “sbknown” command using Stata 15.0, which performs a test of the null hypothesis that the coefficients do not vary over the subsamples defined by the specified known break dates. Table 7 shows the results of this test for each world region and reveal that the selected break years (1985 and 2000) are statistically significant at the 0.01 level in each geographical region meaning that we can reject the null hypothesis of no structural break for the specified dates.

Table 7.
Structural break test

Break dates: 1985 2000	t-statistics
------------------------	--------------

World	245.2867***
OECD	535.8027***
Asia	170.2380***
Latin America	383.5965***

By running the ECM for different periods (adding years one by one to the second period starting in 1986), we can see in Figure 8 for world trade, that the coefficients remain almost the same and are statistically significant. So, this is another evidence indicating that the second break year is 2001 because otherwise we would have observed a significant and major change in the long-run coefficient. As it is not the case, we can be more confident about choosing 2001 as the year when trade elasticity started to change. The fall of trade elasticity for the period 2008-2017 to a figure close to zero is not so apparently incomprehensible because it includes the 2009 GTC and the subsequent years of anaemic growth in world trade.

Figure 8.

Long-run World elasticities for different periods (1986-2017). World

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

Note: blue bars refer to the long-run elasticity for the first period (1986-2000s) and the green ones to the second period (2000s-2017)

Regarding OECD, we have proceeded in the same way, checking the robustness of the break dates, and again the results do not change significantly (see Figure 9). The figures for the 1986-2000s periods (blue bars) are all closed to 2.5 and for the other period (green bars) they fall to figures around 2.0. Curiously, in the case of OECD countries, the period 2008-2017 does not show such a high decrease in elasticity compared to the World case, but this is coherent with

the argument stated above, which mentions that GDP growth amongst OECD countries was also very low.

Figure 9.

Long-run World elasticities for different periods (1986-2017). OECD

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

In reference to the results for Asian countries (Figure 10), we can assert again that ECM coefficients stay almost invariant, showing the big fall in elasticity between the second (blue bars) and third period (green bars).

Figure 10.

Long-run World elasticities for different periods (1986-2017). Asia

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

In line with the results in Table 6, Latin America's additional ECMs (Figure 11) do not show a steady pattern: results corresponding to subsequent ECMs from 1986-2001 are neither statistically significant (light blue) nor do they show a similar result. In the Latin American case, we must be cautious about the existence of a point of time from which trade slowdown takes place.²⁰

²⁰ This robustness check has also been carried out for a year break of 1985, but results have not been included for the sake of simplicity, being available upon request.

Figure 11.

Long-run World elasticities for different periods (1986-2017). Latin America

Source: World Bank and own elaboration

We have used import data when analyzing trade elasticity, but it is possible that regional data exports may show a different pattern. and in consequence. we have checked the robustness of the results so far obtained by running the ECM for export data and for the same periods: the export data's ECM results show a similar pattern, since export elasticity grows from 1986 to 2001 in comparison with the previous period 1970-1985 to fall thereafter (2001-2017) revealing a similar slowdown as in the case for imports (Annex 2). The only exception is for Latin American countries, where long-run export elasticity does not show a relevant slowdown. Additionally, they are significantly lower than in the case of imports, probably due to their high dependency on exporting commodities.

V.- CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this paper is to assess whether the global trade slowdown is fundamentally a structural phenomenon or not. In order to carry this out, we compute an ECM for the World and different regional areas (World, OECD, Asia, and Latin American countries) and for several time periods (1970-1985; 1986-2000; 2001-2017), testing trade-income elasticity shifts over time.

We have been able to detect that the highest trade elasticity was reached in the period 1986-2000, coinciding not accidentally with important structural changes that were positively affecting world trade (liberalizing trade policies, lower transport and logistics costs, and international fragmentation of production processes). In line with other papers, our findings support that the trade slowdown started before the global trade collapse in 2009, although since this year, the slowdown has been more evident.

When we look at different regions, this pattern is quite similar for import and export flows (except for Latin American countries). As for OECD countries, the long-run elasticity does not decrease as much as for the whole world, suggesting that they represent a more cohesive group of countries. Furthermore, the long-run elasticity for imports for the whole period (1970-2017) is somewhat higher than for the whole world. In Asia, results are consistent with the idea that reshoring strategies by firms have affected these countries more, since the coefficient for the slowdown period is lower. As for Latin American countries, apparently import substitution policies adopted during the 1970s explain the feeble relationship between trade and GDP. Thereafter, since the mid-eighties, elasticity started to be similar to the rest of the world values, consistent with the radical change in trade policy. Finally, as in the other cases, in the last period, the long-run relationship decreases.

We think that these conclusions are quite relevant since they corroborate a big shift in the global economy towards less trade and less globalization in general, with potential significant effects in every world area. Provided this change is a persistent one, this will require a considerable structural adjustment in growth models, especially in those countries that are more dependent on trade openness, such as smaller countries, as well as emerging ones.

In our opinion the policy implications of such a big shift are far reaching. Policy makers in son many developed and emerging countries alike that have embraced Export-led growth strategies as a first best option during the last decades by implementing neo-mercantilist policies may change their minds. Achieving strong international competitiveness and a persistent current account surplus trough wage repression, currency devaluation and labour cost reducing FDI may become a less attractive option now. If the globalization process shows signs of exhaustion this may open more space to push for a new policy agenda based on strengthening domestic demand and on enlarging more local capabilities. In the end less trade dependent economies may be more resilient to “exogenous” shocks, more environmentally friendly and even more in accordance with less income inequality.

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Annex 1. List of countries

OECD

Australia	Hungary	Norway
Austria	Iceland	Poland
Belgium	Ireland	Portugal
Canada	Israel	Slovak Republic
Chile	Italy	Slovenia
Czech Republic	Japan	Spain
Denmark	Korea, Rep.	Sweden
Estonia	Latvia	Switzerland
Finland	Luxembourg	Turkey
France	Mexico	United Kingdom
Germany	Netherlands	United States
Greece	New Zealand	

ASIA (EAST ASIA AND PACIFIC & SOUTH ASIA)

Afghanistan	Kiribati	Pakistan
American Samoa	Korea, Rep.	Papua New Guinea
Australia	Lao PDR	Philippines
Bangladesh	Macao SAR, China	Samoa
Bhutan	Malaysia	Singapore
Brunei Darussalam	Maldives	Solomon Islands
Cambodia	Marshall Islands	Sri Lanka
China	Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	Taiwan, China
Fiji	Mongolia	Thailand
French Polynesia	Myanmar	Timor-Leste
Guam	Nauru	Tonga
Hong Kong SAR, China	Nepal	Tuvalu
India	New Caledonia	Vanuatu
Indonesia	New Zealand	Vietnam
Japan	Northern Mariana Islands	

LATIN AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN

Antigua and Barbuda	Costa Rica	Jamaica
Argentina	Cuba	Mexico
Aruba	Curacao	Nicaragua
Bahamas, The	Dominica	Panama
Barbados	Dominican Republic	Paraguay
Belize	Ecuador	Peru
Bolivia	El Salvador	Puerto Rico
Brazil	Grenada	Sint Maarten (Dutch part)
British Virgin Islands	Guatemala	St. Kitts and Nevis
Cayman Islands	Guyana	St. Lucia
Chile	Haiti	St. Martin (French part)
Colombia	Honduras	

St. Vincent and the
Grenadines
Suriname

Trinidad and Tobago
Turks and Caicos Islands
Uruguay

Venezuela, RB
Virgin Islands (U.S.)

Annex 2. ECM estimations using exports of goods and services (2010 \$ constant).

2.1. Testing unit root test for exports of goods and services (2010 \$ constant).

Table 1. Unit Root test. Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test

	Level		First Difference	
	Constant	Trend	Constant	Trend
World (x_t)	-0.897	-2.048	-5.569***	-5.562***
OECD (x_t)	-1.273	-1.618	-5.769***	-5.941***
Asia(x_t)	-1.866	-0.809	-5.620***	-6.223***
Latin America (x_t)	-1.688	-2.479	-4.622***	-4.741***

Note: *, **, *** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively.

Table 2. Unit Root test. Phillips-Perron Test ($z(t)$)

	Level		First Difference	
	Constant	Trend	Constant	Trend
World (x_t)	-1.016	-2.154	-7.163***	-7.168***
OECD (x_t)	-1.482	-1.583	-6.982***	-7.152***
Asia(x_t)	-2.300	-1.146	-7.514***	-8.106***
Latin America (x_t)	-1.561	-2.557	-7.693***	-7.880***

Note: *, **, *** denote the statistical significance at the level of 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively.

2.2 Testing break dates when using exports of goods and services (2010 \$ constant).

Break dates: 1985 2000	t-statistics
World	159.1227 ***
OECD	325.9134 ***
Asia	56.4807***
Latin America	158.3463 ***

2.3. Estimations

Table 1a. World. Exports of goods and services (2010 \$ constant). World Bank

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.125**	-.741**	-.481***	-.191
Long-run elasticity	1.768***	1.354***	2.222***	1.462***
Short-run elasticity	2.156***	.385	1.483***	2.795***
Constant	-3.256	-10.210*	-19.253***	-3.101
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	1.81	2.13	1.68	1.952
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	.535	1.461	.442	.008
Homoscedasticity	10.43	12.34	7.66	14.23
R-squared	.7016	.7619	.8022	.9584
Observations	47	15	15	17

Table 2a. OECD

	1970-2015	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.071	1.465***	-.338**	-.325
Long-run elasticity	2.345***	1.688***	2.592***	2.516***
Short-run elasticity	2.031***	-1.438**	1.211**	1.978***
Constant	-3.110*	-34.09***	-17.39***	-16.076
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	1.89	2.24	2.29	1.08
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	.141	.546	.024	5.934**
Homoscedasticity	15.72*	9.85	7.14	5.22
R-squared	.7272	.9247	.7381	.9008
Observations	47	15	15	17

Table 3a. Asian countries

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.061	-.648*	-.322	-.244*
Long-run elasticity	1.347***	1.673***	2.031***	.914***
Short-run elasticity	1.446***	-.546	1.094***	4.081***
Constant	-.737	-14.040*	-10.457*	.191
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	2.27	1.90	2.10	2.73
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	1.461	.002	1.194	4.171*
Homoscedasticity	11.08	7.68	12.93	9.72
R-squared	.2760	.3407	.6008	.8419
Observations	47	15	15	16

Table 4a. Latin American countries

	1970-2017	1970-1985	1986-2000	2001-2017
Speed of adjustment	-.184*	-.637**	-.021	-.355*
Long-run elasticity	1.539***	1.071***	1.01	.967***
Short-run elasticity	1.101**	.816	.074	1.159***
Constant	-3.184	-2.595	.009	-.195
Durbin-Watson d-statistic	2.13	2.01	1.99	.743
Breusch-Godfrey LM test for serial correlation	.388	.226	.087	11.07***
Homoscedasticity	6.68	7.48	8.51	15.44*
R-squared	.1916	.3969	.011	.5934
Observations	47	15	15	17